
MEMORANDUM

TO: THE CLERK TO THE COMMITTEE ON CONSTITUTIONAL AND PARLIAMENTARY AFFAIRS

FROM: CONCERNED HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS

SUBJECT: POSITION STATEMENT OF HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS ON “THE PROMOTION OF PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS AND GHANAIAN FAMILY VALUES BILL, 2021”

DATE: SEPTEMBER 26, 2021

CC: ALBAN BAGBIN, SPEAKER OF PARLIAMENT, REPUBLIC OF GHANA

Thank you for the opportunity that your committee has provided for concerned groups to submit memoranda to assist you in your deliberations on the above bill.

We are healthcare professionals from various specialties and health fields who have been moved to address this bill to help ensure the safety of patients as well as protect access to health services to all Ghanaians. We reviewed the bill and have come to a consensus that the proposed bill contains several provisions that raise significant medical, scientific, and public health concerns. On that account we believe the bill if passed can cause damage to the health and well-being of many citizens with the queer community bearing the major brunt of its impact.

A former Justice of our Supreme Court, Justice Kweku Etrewe Amua-Sekyi in a judgment on the case: *New Patriotic Party vrs Inspector-General of Police* [1993] 2 GLR 459 - 509¹ in 1993 wrote; “*Most restrictions on our personal Liberty which, after years of repression, we have come to accept, are inconsistent with democratic norms. Except in times of war, or when a state of emergency has been declared, it cannot be right for any agency of the executive to suppress free expression of any opinion. However unpopular that opinion may be. The believer in absolutism and the anarchist, those who support and those who are opposed to abortion, those that favour equal rights for women - **yes, lesbians and homosexuals too** - are entitled to the free expression of their views, and the right to assemble and demonstrate in support of those views and to propagate their views...*” With the above clear and strong opinion, which is as valid today as it was then, expressed by one of our eminent prior supreme court Justice in 1993, our elected

¹ *New Patriotic Party v Inspector General of Police, Or g na jur sd ct on, ILDC 2548 (GH 1993), [1993 94] 2 GLR 459 SC, 30th November 1993, Ghana; Supreme Court*

members of Parliament will need to exercise more caution with a bill such as the one proposed.

The LGBTQ community that the bill targets is a very small minority group in the Ghanaian society, incapable of having a significant influence on the culture and way of life of most Ghanaians yet faces significant discrimination and difficulties in their day to day lives, including limited access to healthcare at various levels. This was well articulated in focus group interviews performed in Accra, Kumasi and Manya Krobo in 2017 [Kushwaha, Sameer, et al, 2017]². The bill proposed by the Honorable Member of Parliament for Ningo Prampram constituency Samuel Nartey George will make an already bad situation an almost impossible one. Many members of our group have significant experience in the care of individuals from the LGBT+ community and can attest to the profound way this bill can negatively impact the health of the community. As concerned healthcare professionals, we would like to bring these issues and concerns to your attention and to that of parliament as they deliberate on this bill.

Below is a point-by-point summary of some of our main concerns, with respect to the health implications of “The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Family Values Bill, presented with excerpts from the Bill.”

Duty to promote proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values

This section of the bill implies that entities, such as, teachers, parents and guardians, the church, the executive, the legislature, the judiciary, and relevant bodies are required to promote the content of the bill. It is ambiguous enough to include healthcare professionals and, thus, will make individuals in the LGBT+ community even less likely to go to healthcare facilities for care, or to speak honestly to their healthcare professionals. Most of us healthcare professionals have codes and oaths such as the Hippocratic oath for physicians and the Nightingale Pledge which allows us to hold patient information sacrosanct. Unfortunately, most individuals are not aware of these oaths and pledges. Experts, including some Ghanaians have recognized these problems already and have documented these difficulties and their impact on health prevention in these communities. [Gyamerah, Akua O., et al, 2020]³. This bill will push our citizens, who are LGBT+ even further away from our healthcare system.

Duty to report.

Like the above section, this will make it difficult for community members to seek needed healthcare. Many of us who have worked in the United States know of similar situations related to undocumented migrants in the US not seeking care for fear doctors and healthcare workers will give their names to immigration officials even though that is not the true (Berk, Marc L., and Claudia L. Schur, 2001)⁴. The bill will create a culture of

² Kushwaha, Sameer, et al. "“But the moment they find out that you are MSM...”: a qualitative investigation of HIV prevention experiences among men who have sex with men (MSM) in Ghana’s health care system." *BMC Public Health* 17.1 (2017): 1-18.

³ Gyamerah, Akua O., et al. "Stigma, discrimination, violence, and HIV testing among men who have sex with men in four major cities in Ghana." *AIDS care* 32.8 (2020): 1036-1044.

⁴ Berk, Marc L., and Claudia L. Schur. "The effect of fear on access to care among undocumented Latino immigrants." *Journal of Immigrant Health* 3.3 (2001): 151-156.

mistrust between health professionals and the community. This is not how we should be relating to a community who are already less likely to seek services. This was seen in Senegal with criminalization of same sex relationships [Poteat, Tonia, et al, 2011]⁵. As healthcare workers we hope our country will not effectively close the doors of our health system on a community that has significant health issues requiring special attention.

Prohibition of LGBTTTQQAAP+ and related activities.

This provision of the bill stipulates punishments for providing or participating in the provision of a surgical or other procedure that is intended to create a sexual category other than the sexual category assigned at birth except in the case of correcting a biological anomaly. If this bill becomes law, this provision will put the health of individuals requiring such services for medical reasons, whether in Ghana, when they are available, or elsewhere at risk. Thus, individuals requiring, for example, hormonal therapy will resort to unlicensed and unregulated facilities, manned by unscrupulous and untrained individuals as seen in other countries with similar policy barriers [Maschião, Luca F., et al, 2020]⁶. It is critically important that the healthcare system is open and non-discriminatory to allow all citizens to have access to healthcare, provided by trained qualified professionals.

Prohibiting of funding or sponsorship for prohibited activities and Disbandment of LGBTTTQQAAP+ groups, societies, and associations, club or organisation.

These two provisions will close off all avenues of funding and other activities used by many organizations to develop HIV prevention programs for the community. We believe that these provisions of this bill, which, ironically, states an intent to reduce HIV will rather increase the risk. This is evidenced by the fact that criminalization in several African and Caribbean countries appears to lead to increased HIV risk and made control more difficult [Hagopian, Amy, et al., 2017]⁷.

Access to medical help and treatment of the accused

This section of the proposed bill purports to offer voluntary treatment to LGBT+ individuals and will reduce the sentences of those who elect to get treatment. This provision should be irrelevant since these citizens are not criminals and their lifestyle should not be criminalized. We believe that criminalizing them will be a violation of their constitutional rights and a breach of international human rights laws. Such a provision will also result in significant psychological trauma to the impacted individuals, by subjecting them to unnecessary dubious, scientifically, and medically unproven

⁵ Poteat, Tonia, et al. "HIV risk among MSM in Senegal: a qualitative rapid assessment of the impact of enforcement laws that criminalize same sex practices." *PoS one* 6.12 (2011): e28760.

⁶ Maschião, Luca F., et al. "Nonprescribed sex hormone use among trans women: The complex interplay of public policies, social context, and discrimination." *Transgender Health* 5.4 (2020): 205-215.

⁷ Hagopian, Amy, et al. "Antihomosexuals at on and HIV related stigma in African nations: what has been the role of PEPFAR?." *Global health action* 10.1 (2017): 1306391

“treatments” with doubtful clinical benefit [Meanley Steven et al, 2020]⁸. There is a reported close to 2 – 2.5 times increase in psychological conditions in adult gay men exposed to these “treatments”. The mere mention of treatment for homosexuality pathologizes same sex relationships. In this context, we would like to emphasize that the Diagnostic Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 5th Edition (DSM-5) does not classify homosexuality as a mental disorder. In fact, the DSM has not classified homosexuality as a disease since 1973 [Drescher, Jack., 2015]⁹. There are some who mention the high rates of suicide as a justification that homosexuality be classified as a mental disorder. These arguments however fail to state that the increased harassment associated with laws such as the one being proposed in Ghana, as well as the intense organized negative public antagonism against the community is driving these increased suicide rates [Marx, Robert A., et al, 2021]¹⁰.

We have many more concerns with regards to this bill but will leave the overall assessment of the bill to our legal colleagues who are best qualified to do so.

If the event that your parliament decides to pass this bill despite all the above stated concerns, we propose that prior to signing this bill into law an impact assessment specifically focused on the unintended health consequences be implemented by an independent body.

We will also welcome an opportunity to discuss these issues further with relevant members of this committee or any of those sponsoring this bill. It appears to us that this bill was proposed to help address social issues of concern within the country. We can understand these concerns but believe these problems can be appropriately addressed outside the legal system. We will await your response and action on the issues raised in this letter

Yours Sincerely

 ah, MBChB, MPH, FACP, for the supporting healthcare professionals

⁸ Meanley, Steven, et al. "Lifetime exposure to conversion therapy and psychosocial health among middle and older adult men who have sex with men." *The Gerontologist* 60.7 (2020): 1291-1302.

⁹ Drescher, Jack. "Out of DSM: Depathologizing homosexuality." *Behavioral Sciences* 5.4 (2015): 565-575.

¹⁰ Marx, Robert A., et al. "Predictors of sexual victimization and suicide ideation among transgender and gender nonconforming adolescents." *Psychology & Sexuality* 12.1-2 (2021): 79-95.

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